

Normalizing Mercenarism as Business: The Process of Regulating Private Military and Security Companies at the United Nations Level

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Abstract

This article examines efforts to regulate private military and security companies (PMSCs) in different UN fora since 2005, in order to understand the processes that led to a significant dilution of initial regulatory ambitions. The analysis of the proceedings of the three working groups relevant to this process suggests a decreasing level of ambition concerning the creation of a binding international instrument that would ensure the compliance of PMSCs with international human rights standards and international humanitarian law. This article argues that the dilution of strong arguments in favor of binding regulation can be attributed to three types of factors: the shifting of the debate from experts and activists to state representatives; the existence of a North-South cleavage on the issue at the intergovernmental level; and the emergence of competing regulatory fora such as private governance by the industry itself (the International Code of Conduct Association) and the Swiss-led initiative for the creation of a soft law instrument (the Montreux Document). Thus, despite an initial general consensus on the threat that unregulated PMSCs pose to human rights, the structure of the regulation process led to a diluted outcome wherein human rights issues were relegated behind the interests of both hegemonic states and the industry.

Keywords

private security; human rights; international humanitarian law; governance; United Nations

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Introduction

Private military and security companies (PMSCs) have often been criticized in the International Relations (IR) literature. First, the process through which they take on inherently State functions in the fields of security and defense makes the state more susceptible to weakening in the long term (Singer, 2005; Verkuil, 2007); second, they are associated with mercenarism, which is not a socially acceptable phenomenon in international politics²; third, some have a very poor human rights record documented in academic literature (Torroja, 2017)³. However, because of a general lack of regulation of their activities, they enjoy a great extent of freedom in the conduct of their business. Although national legislation exists in several countries to address the phenomenon (Gumedze, 2008; Krahnemann & Abzhaparova, 2010; White 2016), the transnational character of the industry makes it ineffective in covering all the contested aspects of PMSC actions. At the international level, while there is a consensus both in the academic literature and among decision-makers that PMSCs must be regulated, to date, no international legal instrument exists to put limits on states, international organizations, or private entities resorting to such companies; to ensure that these companies respect human rights and international humanitarian law; and to allow victims of human rights violations committed by these companies or their employees to access remedies. In other words, PMSCs cannot be held accountable in international law for gross human rights violations.

How is it possible that despite the consensus on the need to regulate, the creation of international regulation has been so slow and ineffective? What *happened* during the process that hindered the emergence of international norms in the field? What issues were at stake that prevented state consensus on regulation? How and why did the discourse within the various UN bodies change? And from a wider perspective, what does this process tell us about the phenomenon of the evolution of norms?

This article reconstitutes the evolution of UN deliberations on the regulation of PMSCs beginning with the initial discussion of the issue by the UN Working Group on Mercenaries after its creation in 2005, with an eye to understanding the different perspectives and positions of participating actors, including experts, states, businesses, and NGOs. While the material object of this study is the regulation of PMSCs in UN fora, its formal object and more theoretical ambition is to understand the process of evolution of norms at the UN (in this case, the process of norm dilution), with an emphasis on both the various actors with their specific interests and the conditions that favor or hinder the success of accountability efforts.

The article provides an in-depth analysis of the three most relevant UN working groups: the *UN Working Group on Mercenaries* (hereafter WGM), the *UN Open-Ended Intergovernmental Working Group to consider the possibility of elaborating an international regulatory framework, including the option of a legally binding instrument on the regulation, monitoring, and oversight of the activities of PMSCs* (hereafter OEIGWG1) and the *UN Open-Ended Intergovernmental Working Group to elaborate the content of an international regulatory framework on the regulation, monitoring, and oversight of the activities of PMSCs* (hereafter OEIGWG2). The empirical basis for the analysis is constituted by the documents produced by these three working groups throughout their existence. The article traces the evolution of the PMSC *problematique* and highlights the development, participants, and internal

² The International Convention against the Recruitment, Use, Financing and Training of Mercenaries, signed in 1989, entered into force in 2001, and it has 54 parties. It is considered a “strong norm, weak law” (Percy, 2007).

³ Blackwater, CACI International, Titan Corp and the Wagner Group are only a few examples of companies that have been proven to have breached human rights.

dynamics of these working groups, to show how the evolution of the language used in their documents mirrors the downshifting of the WGM's initial ambitions from establishing an international binding instrument for the regulation of PMSCs toward the creation of a very loose and ambiguous "Zero draft instrument on an international regulatory framework." The focus of the discussion here centers on the issue of accountability for PMSCs, and not on the more technical aspects of licensing and registration, which also constitute important points of discussion throughout the process of establishing regulations.

The main hypothesis proposed in this contribution is that the emergence of a binding international regulatory framework for PMSCs is hindered by three types of cleavages, or tensions, whose dynamics diluted the content of the debates around the issue. First, the cleavage between experts and state representatives: there is a striking difference in approach between the WGM and the OEIGWs, with the former pushing for a maximalist perspective on regulation and the latter getting tangled up in endless discussions about the definitions of terms already clarified in the WGM or inflexible statements with little room for compromise. Second, the differences among UN member-states – ranging from a maximalist position of forbidding PMSCs altogether to a minimalist position that supports the *status quo* of ambiguous regulation of different types (either national or self-regulation by the business) – have rendered any consensus impossible. Third, the multiplication of fora that took on the project of creating a framework for the regulation of PMSCs, either in the sphere of soft law or of private governance, over time further diluted the initial proposal to create an international binding instrument.

In recent years, the *locus* of norm-emergence has thus shifted from the UN to private organizations, such as the business-led International Code of Conduct Association (ICoCA) or Western-dominated negotiation fora, such as the Swiss initiative that created the Montreux Document. The consequence of this evolution has been the extreme dilution of any initial regulatory ambitions and the degeneration of the anti-mercenary norm in international practice. Thus, the novelty of this research consists in offering an empirically informed assessment of the process through which emerging regulations, even those supported by a strong customary basis (such as international norms on mercenarism), have become diluted to the point of irrelevance in the face of private interests.

Relevant literature

This article contributes to at least two debates in the academic literature dedicated to the regulation of private security. The first tackles the general issue of norm evolution – or rather, in this case, involution. Some authors argue that the norm against mercenary activity has 'degenerated incrementally' up to a point where states have begun to use mercenaries in the form of private military and security companies – that is, the norm has disappeared (Panke & Petersohn, 2012). The reasons for the degenerescence of the norm are, according to the two authors, the imprecision and ambiguity of the norm, as well as the existence of what they call 'curbing mechanisms', that is, particular circumstances that make it difficult to apply (Panke & Petersohn, 2012: 723). In this case, the particular circumstances emphasized by the authors are the cost-effectiveness of resorting to private contractors, both in terms of funding and political costs, which made states more willing to resort to PMSCs (Panke & Petersohn, 2012: 730).

Other authors argue that 'norms rarely die' – they are rather resilient, and only a long historical perspective, as well as a contextualization of the normative and social structures in which norms operate, can shed light on how norms undergo a process of transformation (Percy & Sandholtz, 2022). Specifically, for the anti-mercenary norm, these authors show that it has not disappeared, because mercenarism has not become 'legally and morally acceptable' (Percy & Sandholtz, 2022: 939). It is the

notion of ‘mercenary’ itself that changed, allowing PMSCs to be excluded from this category. Thus, the notion only covers individual mercenaries, and not established businesses, while also including active engagement in offensive combat – which is formally forbidden in the case of PMSCs⁴.

Our contribution to this debate sheds light on some dimensions of the process of the evolution of the anti-mercenary norm that have not been previously discussed. Thus, we emphasize the discursive aspects of the dilution of the norm – how the language used in the debates in different UN fora transformed over time as a result, first, of opposing views of experts and states’ representatives; second, of different states; and third, of states’ and business’ representatives. We demonstrate that the evolution of the debates at the UN level, from 2005 until 2022, indicates a visible degeneration of the anti-mercenary norm. “Strong norm, weak law”: this is how Sarah Percy characterized in 2007 the international norm against mercenarism (Percy, 2007). Ever since, the incapacity of states to agree upon explicit legal provisions to address the activity of PMSCs has also led to the weakening of the norm, if not to its disappearance.

Other factors have also contributed to the dilution of the anti-mercenary norm. According to the more general literature on norm-emergence, the consolidation of norms is facilitated by the support of hegemonic powers (Ikenberry & Kupchan, 1990) or the activism of transnational advocacy networks (Keck & Sikkink, 1998; Sandholtz, 2017). In the case of PMSC regulation, the analysis below shows that both incentives were absent.

The second debate in the PMSC literature that our contribution engages with concerns the factors that facilitate the success of the regulatory process. Different approaches have been proposed in the academic literature to account for the effectiveness and legitimacy of attempts to regulate PMSCs, some of them revealing how regulations are structured by the circulation of social norms and ideas (Boggero, 2018), others - by dynamics of power (Prem, 2020). The first scholar to map the relationship between the state and PMSCs in the context of the privatization of security (2005), Deborah Avant also analyzed (from the perspective of what she calls “pragmatism and network theory”) how the process of regulation was seemingly facilitated by the low ambition and soft law approach of the “Swiss Initiative” that culminated in the Montreux Document in 2008 and the creation of the International Code of Conduct in 2009, which were both presented as regulatory successes (Avant, 2021). The opposite conclusion was reached by Berenike Prem, who emphasizes that, in multi-stakeholder settings, the field is likely to be structured and controlled by the most powerful organizations, resulting in a regulatory framework that favors corporate and powerful state interests, while marginalizing the demands of citizens and grassroots NGOs (Prem, 2021). While Avant simultaneously describes the “Swiss Initiative” as a success from the point of view of regulation and downplays the position of the UN Special Rapporteur for Mercenaries and the WGM (Avant, 2016: 334-335), Prem insists that the process through which the site of norm negotiation was shifted from the UN to the “Swiss Initiative” had itself a “disciplining effect” on the participant NGOs (Prem, 2020; Prem, 2021: 346) and contributed to both the legitimization of the industry and its loose and permissive (self-)regulation.

The perspective of this article differs from both authors cited above, as we do not try to account for the entire landscape of different types of actors involved in regulation efforts, but instead focus only on the institution that has been the main *locus* of international law-making after 1945: the UN and its different working groups related to the PMSC regulatory process. In contrast to the existing literature, this article provides the first analysis of the three UN working groups dedicated to the issue

⁴ However, the authors acknowledge that this distinction is problematic in practice – p. 939.

of PMSCs as interconnected, but often competing fora for PMSC regulation. Drawing on the work of Berenike Prem, my contribution aims to prove that not only *forum shifting* from the UN to private fora such as the Swiss Initiative, but also a shift within the UN itself – which transferred the issue of regulation from the Working Group on the Use of Mercenaries, long known as one of the most vocal supporters of the creation of a binding instrument for PMSC regulation, to several open-ended working groups – led to the legitimation of the industry and the promotion of its interests. This process also shifted the weight from experts toward state representatives, which on the one hand greatly diluted the substantive content of debates, and on the other hand introduced greater fragmentation/heterogeneity in the positions of the different participants in rulemaking. Thus, forum shifting can be understood not only as a process but precisely as a *strategy* intentionally employed by stronger actors to promote the weakening of regulations or the advancement of their own regulatory preferences – a strategy also seen in negotiations over trade regimes and intellectual property policies (Benvenisti & Downs, 2007; Helfer, 2004; Sell, 2011).

Regulation of PMSCs: what is at stake?

Before engaging with the heart of the matter, several issues must be clarified. First, the existence and functions of PMSCs are not completely unregulated. To date, there are three forms of regulation: through national legislation, a state-endorsed non-binding international Document, or private governance. Several states have adopted national frameworks for the industry; the most elaborated examples include legislation in the United States, Switzerland, South Africa, and Australia (A/HRC/36/47). However, national legislations are diverse and inconsistent, leading to gaps in accountability since companies can choose to register in countries with more permissive legislation. Another issue is that PMSCs rarely engage in gross human rights violations in states considered consolidated democracies, such as those that have previously enacted such legislation. Instead, they occur in places where a state's capacity to enforce the law is weak or where the state itself wishes to limit phenomena connected to domestic turmoil. Any judicial interventions against the actions of PMSCs would thus require the legislations of home states to enact provisions allowing extraterritorial jurisdiction, which is very rarely the case.

Efforts at international regulation have also been made outside the UN – but with questionable results. The two most influential are worth mentioning here. The first is an initiative by the Swiss government and the International Committee of the Red Cross, with seventeen participating states, which led to the signing of the *Montreux Document on Pertinent International Legal Obligations and Good Practices for States Related to Operations of PMSCs During Armed Conflict* in 2008. The Document has thus far been endorsed by 58 states and three international organizations. It is non-binding and quite loose in its provisions – a mere collection of good practices, with very limited reference to the standards of due diligence. The Document does not specify access to remedies and lacks obligations for contracting and home states. In fact, it plainly states that it “should not be interpreted (...) as creating or developing new obligations under international law.” There are also important problems related to the drafting process, which might have biased the Document toward the interests of its participants. Most of the seventeen drafting states were from the Global North, while the rest were states in which PMSCs with a dubious record of accountability operate in circumstances that suggest their links to extractive industries. Many participants could hardly be considered independent at the time (among them: Angola, Sierra Leone, Afghanistan, and Iraq). The process was marked by intense lobbying by industry players (including the International Peace Operation Association (IPOA), a beautifully-branded syndicate of PMSCs, which expressed its

satisfaction with the outcome). The main contribution of the Montreux Document is, however, to have clarified the distinctions between the contracting, territorial and home states of PMSCs and to set standards for licensing.

The other relevant international document that attempts to provide a framework for regulating PMSCs is the *International Code of Conduct for Private Security Providers* (ICoC), a private governance initiative led by an industry association created under Swiss law in 2010. The Code directly refers to the “Respect, Protect and Remedy” framework elaborated by John Ruggie, Special Representative of the UN Secretary-General for Business and Human Rights, which has been heavily criticized for its soft approach (Deva, 2013), but otherwise does not address the problem of human rights violations. In its formulations, the ICoC is ultimately more an ode to PMSCs and their efficiency than an instrument for regulating them and holding them accountable. While the Montreux Document is addressed at states, the Code was created by the corporations themselves, a form of voluntary self-regulation. As is manifest from the brief description of these two initiatives, they are even less efficient than national legislations when it comes to addressing the core issue, namely accountability for human rights violations.

At the heart of the struggle for regulation are several contentious issues that create cleavages between various types of stakeholders. The first is the legitimacy of the entire industry – contested or at least questioned by WGM experts, various scholars, and NGOs, and supported by certain states, representatives of the industry, lobbyists, and certain legal and political scholars. The emergence of the Montreux Document and the ICoC ended any questions about the legitimacy of the industry in the debates; it has not been questioned since 2011. As Berenike Prem underlined, “governance initiatives strengthen the perspective of stakeholders that consider PMSCs as normal and legitimate security actors” (Prem, 2021: 345). Thus, the practice of contracting PMSCs has become embedded in the structure of the post-modern warfare and security paradigm, and is thus taken for granted. Although the private military and security industry is intimately linked to issues of life and death and is very human rights-sensitive, there is a tendency to compare it to – and even assimilate it with – a business like any other, a discursive shift that occurs through the introduction of references to the General Principles on Business and Human Rights (the above-mentioned “Respect, Protect and Remedy” framework).

The second contentious issue concerns the existence of “inherently state functions” that – in principle – should not be subcontracted under any circumstances because the very sovereignty of states would thus be affected (on the specific issue of PMSCs, see Verkuil, 2007; an updated discussion on the privatization of state functions in Mégret, 2021). These include direct participation in hostilities or the right to detain and interrogate prisoners.

The third involves a more abstract question: Who governs? Can the international community rely on the goodwill of various industries to self-regulate? Or, taking the opposing view, should the international community create binding legislation for states that otherwise could regulate PMSCs at a national level? The influence of emerging actors – such as corporations, advocacy networks, and NGOs – in the process of international governance has become more and more visible in recent years (Avant, Finnemore, & Sell, 2010), while, in parallel, corporations have developed new strategies to gain greater influence on policies and governance, for example by creating NGOs themselves to intervene in policy-making processes as independent civil society actors –so-called BINGOs, business and industry NGOs (on the role of BINGOs in international regulation, see Birchall, 2020; Vormedal, 2008). While this article does not address the issue directly, it will shed some light on the balance of power between various types of international actors.

Last, but not least, at the heart of the issue of regulation of PMSCs lies the possibility of holding them accountable, as legal persons, for gross violations of human rights. While all participants in the regulatory process agree in principle on the need for accountability, the practical considerations have been much more resistant to consensus, as various branches of the law each bring different perspectives (human rights law, international humanitarian law, business, and human rights law) and different elements of legal doctrine (extraterritorial jurisdiction; due diligence; corporate liability) become involved. While these debates are fascinating in their argumentation, they are not the object of the study here, as the emphasis remains on the *political* processes, more than on the legal disputes surrounding regulation.

The experts have spoken: the UN Working Group on the use of mercenaries and the pressures to regulate

The UN Working Group on Mercenaries was the first UN body to propose and promote the creation of an international binding instrument for the regulation of PMSCs, in an effort to raise awareness about the danger of externalizing certain core state functions to PMSCs. This section will discuss how the WGM produced numerous reports that documented the pernicious role of PMSCs at a global level, argued for UN-binding regulations and criticized the attempts at self-regulation by the industry.

The WGM was created in 2005 to replace the function of the special rapporteur on the use of mercenaries, which existed between 1987 and 2005. The first special rapporteur, Enrique Bernales Ballesteros – a Peruvian politician, professor of social sciences, and member of the Revolutionary Socialist Party – had a maximalist perspective on the need to limit the phenomenon of mercenarism, including PMSCs, and demanded the widening of the definition of the term beyond what was included in the 1989 Convention. The second special rapporteur, Shaista Shameen from Fiji, had her mandate (and the post itself) terminated under unclear circumstances after one year (del Prado, 2008: 432; del Prado suggests that the termination was the result of lobbying by the private military industry), but was later included in the WGM. The establishment of the working group was, from the beginning, contentious, since Western countries voted against it, arguing that the issue of mercenaries needed to be dealt with by a different UN body – the Sixth Committee of the UN General Assembly or the legal committee (del Prado, 2008: 431). The creation of the Working Group must also be put in the context of the elaboration in 1989 of the *Convention against the Recruitment, Use, Financing and Training of Mercenaries*, which only entered into force in 2001 (with only 22 signatories). The negotiation of the Convention also sparked debates about the equation of private military companies with mercenaries. This discussion has not yet been definitively settled. Despite the striking resemblances between mercenary activity and PMSC activity, corporate lobbyists and states that take advantage from working with PMSCs instead of regular armies have managed to embed the argument that private military and security constitute a legitimate business in the inter-governmental discussions that have taken place since 2011, as will be shown below.

The WGM is composed of five independent members, each representing one of the geopolitical regional groups at the UN (Africa, Asia-Pacific, Eastern Europe, Latin America and the Caribbean, and Western Europe and Others), elected by the UN Human Rights Council (HRC). Over time, the WGM has maintained gender balance: of the seventeen members who rotated so far, nine have been women. Some of its members were prominent academic figures who also published on the subject (Aparac 2018; del Prado, 2008; 2011; Karska, 2016; Katz & Maffai, 2015; MacLeod, 2008; 2022; Patel, 2020); others were activists for human rights (Gabor Rona, Human Rights First; Ravindran Daniel, Asian Forum for Human Rights and Development).

Although it began by attempting to grapple with the issue of mercenarism, most of the WGM's work has been dedicated to PMSCs, and not to mercenaries more widely. In so doing, experts from the WGM constitute their *field*, in a Bourdieusian sense. The issue of PMSCs emerged on the WGM agenda in the early stages of the discussion. Its first yearly report, issued in 2006, mentions the "grey area" of the legislation covering them and urges member-states not to relinquish their prerogatives in the fields of police and military (A/61/34: 14-16). It might appear peculiar that, despite the fact issues surrounding PMSCs are deeply contentious (because they undermine state sovereignty and defense capabilities; because they cannot be held accountable for their actions in remote territories, *etc.*), the issue of the human rights abuses by these companies was first invoked from the perspective of individuals employed by PMSCs whose rights were infringed upon – and addressed with reference to the UN draft Norms on the Responsibilities of Transnational Companies and Other Business Enterprises with Regard to Human Rights (E/CN.4/2006/11/Add.1: 10). This is relevant in order to acknowledge the link between issues of *business and human rights*, on the one hand (addressed by the UN WG on Elaborating a Binding Instrument on Transnational Corporations and Human Rights – open-ended, established in 2014), and the topic of PMSCs. It is a more surreptitious way to raise the issue of the damage caused by PMSCs from inside the capitalist narrative itself (which accepts that corporations should respect labor rights) instead of arguing that this type of business is inherently illegitimate – a stance liable to attract staunch critique from advocates of the free market. Nonetheless, addressing the issue of employee rights also clearly signals that the industry is accepted as a legitimate business sector – which, on the one hand, might help those who want to hold these companies accountable, but, on the other hand, surrenders the initial position that these companies should not exist or should be assimilated with mercenaries.

Beyond the problem of employee rights, some of the other issues already raised in the first report were the human rights violations at Abu Ghraib, the links between PMSCs, extractive industries, and African governments, and allegations of human rights infringements by PMSCs working with different UN bodies. The first report of the Working Group even led to a GA Resolution that same year (A/RES/61/151) that "requests all States to exercise the utmost vigilance against any kind of recruitment, training, hiring, or financing of mercenaries by private companies offering international military consultancy and security services, as well as to impose a specific ban on such companies intervening in armed conflicts or actions to destabilize constitutional regimes." It was the romantic age, when the principled illegitimacy of PMSCs could still be articulated and presented in a UN forum such as the GA, before their existence – and the practice of hiring PMSCs engaged in by states and international organizations – was normalized.

Throughout the eighteen years of its existence, the Group has carried out numerous activities, including field trips and communications to governments requesting clarifications, and the production of a large number of documents. It studied national legislations on the matter, from regional-based and comparative perspectives, as well as the use of PMSCs by the UN, their role in Afghanistan and Iraq, and their links to the extractive industry (always with an eye to their accountability for human rights violations). The language used to describe the activities of the PMSCs invariably emphasizes the problems their existence raises: the fact that they do not treat their employees fairly; they cannot be held accountable for human rights violations; they tend to subcontract their activities and thus earn money from speculation; their activities are not under parliamentary control; they sometimes stimulate demand for their services in low-intensity conflict zones; and they on occasion present themselves as peace operators, using that label to obtain public funds from UN peacekeeping and development aid (A/HRC/4/42; A/HRC/7/7). During the early years of its existence, the documents

produced by the WGM reveal a normative approach that emphasizes the negative impact of PMSCs and the urgency for states to decide which governmental functions simply cannot be outsourced. A call upon states to convene a high-level roundtable to discuss the legitimacy of PMSCs appears in all reports until 2008, the year the Montreux Document was released. It marks a turning point in the discussion because the effect of the Swiss Initiative is the confirmation of the legitimacy of contracting private military and security corporations by states. The Montreux process and the ensuing document were heavily criticized by the WGM in its 2009 Report to the GA (A/HRC/10/14), which underlined several shortcomings: the limited participation in the drafting process (only seventeen countries, the majority of which were Western states that represented 80% of PMSCs operating worldwide); the intense lobbying by the industry and the IPOA's subsequent satisfaction with the result; the document's limited application to situations of armed conflict, in terms of respect for international humanitarian law; the lack of reference to standards of due diligence; no mention of access to remedies; the lack of obligations for contracting and home states, and a too heavy burden on territorial states (i.e. those where PMSCs operate).

At the same time, the WGM began to raise the issue of the creation of a new international convention that would address the regulation of PMSCs. It argued that the UN Convention on Mercenaries remained an important instrument but failed to address the particular problems of the status of PMSC employees and their accountability for human rights violations. The idea was first mentioned – very cautiously – in 2008: “A new international instrument, possibly in the format of a new UN convention on PMSCs, may be required” (A/63/325). Without further ado, the WGM drafted this instrument and proposed it to the General Assembly in 2011 (A/HRC/WG.10/1/2), which responded by creating an open-ended intergovernmental working group to negotiate the idea and the text. When addressing the OEIGWG1, at the beginning of its mandate, the WGM made a strong plea in favor of a binding international regulatory instrument, arguing that “self-regulation cannot address the problem of impunity,” that “national legislation is not sufficient to address the problem of impunity,” that “current international law does not sufficiently address the issue of PMSCs” and that “victims should have the right to an effective remedy” (A/HRC/WG.10/CRP.1). From 2011 onwards, the WGM worked in parallel first with the OEIGWG1, and then with the OEIGWG2.

The conclusion that an international instrument was necessary was also supported by the study trips conducted by the WGM in PMSC contracting, territorial and home states. In the resulting “Global study on national regulatory frameworks and legislation on PMSCs (2013-2016)” (A/HRC/36/47), the WGM found that national legislations were weak, “patchy and inconsistent”, and therefore “cannot address human rights concerns effectively,” forcing it to “reiterate its call for an internationally legally binding instrument.” Completed in 2017, six years after its demand for a convention, this report highlights how experts continued their efforts to lobby for the creation of an international binding regulatory instrument after the creation of the OEIGWGs, providing new evidence every year in favor of their arguments. Notably, in 2018, the WGM's *Mercenarism and PMSCs* study notes “a lack of transparency regarding the use of private security companies by the UN, with little to no information on the number or name of the companies being contracted or details regarding unarmed services” (A/HRC/NONE/2018/40: 22).

One of the WGM's strongest claims, reiterated in several documents over the years, is that there are certain functions of the state that cannot under any circumstances be outsourced, namely: “direct participation in hostilities, waging war and/or combat operations, taking prisoners, law-making, espionage, intelligence, knowledge transfer with military, security and policing application, use of and other activities related to weapons of mass destruction and police powers, especially the powers of

arrest or detention including the interrogation of detainees” (Draft Convention, art. 2(i)). This list is quite long, and quite a few of these functions are already being performed by PMSCs, such as, for example, the interrogation of prisoners at Abu Ghraib. The WGM approach – although very principled in theoretical terms and very solidly argued from the perspective of the impact of these developments on the nature of the state itself – seems to be superseded by developments in practice, which made certain authors doubt that the issue would ever receive sufficient support from states (White, 2011: 137-140). Indeed, the subject would no longer appear at all in discussions within the OEIGWGs, which highlights the broad (and somewhat inexplicable) consensus surrounding states renouncing some of their core attributes in favor of private entities.

Although the WGM’s major focus has remained on PMSCs, by 2015, it began to address other subjects as well, with an ever more tempered approach that was also consistent with the cautious stance evinced by the open-ended intergovernmental working group. Nevertheless, the WGM continued to study various aspects of the PMSC activity in depth, such as its relationship to extractive industries (A/HCR/42/42), the gendered human rights impact of PMSCs activity (A/74/244), or their role in border management (A/HRC/45/9).

The states negotiate: the open-ended intergovernmental working groups and the obstacles to regulation

The *Draft of a Possible Convention on Private Military and Security Companies* was presented by the WGM to the HRC in 2011 and constituted the basis for the work of the *UN Open-Ended Intergovernmental Working Group to consider the possibility of elaborating an international regulatory framework, including the option of a legally binding instrument on the regulation, monitoring and oversight of the activities of PMSCs* (OEIGWG1). Composed of 49 articles, the draft is a carefully elaborated outline for a binding international convention. Working from a maximalist perspective, it contains 17 definitions for the terms with which it operates, clarifying the distinction between military and security services, between contracting states, states of operation, home states, and third states, as well as the expression “inherently state functions” which cannot be delegated to PMSCs (the text actually mentions this interdiction no less than three times, in articles 2(i), 4.3 and 9). Unlike the WGM, which is composed of experts, the open-ended intergovernmental working groups are composed of state representatives, who logically represent state interests; similarly, while discussions inside the WGM engage with expert opinions, the intergovernmental working groups take the form of negotiations and (often inflexible) assertions of state positions on any given matter.

The OEIGWG1 held a total of six sessions over the course of its existence between 2011 and 2017. The first was dedicated to presentations by experts, their vast majority of whom were former or present members of the WGM, but also from DCAF/Geneva Center for Security Sector Governance and the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC). Interestingly, the Special Adviser to John Ruggie, Special Representative of the Secretary-General for Business and Human Rights (BHR), also gave a presentation, in which he emphasized the importance of the „Protect, Respect and Remedy” framework, highlighting once more the link between the issue of PMSCs and BHR – one of the pathways for the normalization of PMSCs as a business like almost any other. Furthermore, Ruggie’s approach itself has been criticized for “undermining the goal of making companies legally accountable for human rights violations” (Deva, 2013: 79). An entire day was dedicated to “informal consultations”. 69 states from across the globe were present, including important international actors such as the United States, the United Kingdom, China, and the Russian Federation. The EU and the African Union participated as international organizations, along with a series of NGOs: the Agence Suisse de

Cooperation Development Économique Nord-sud, the Al-Hakim Foundation, the Association of World Citizens, the International Commission of Jurists (ICJ), the International Peace Bureau, Human Rights First and the World Federation of Trade Unions (only NGOs with consultative status at ECOSOC could attend).

According to the minutes of the meeting, “it was emphasized (...) that questions regarding the appropriateness and type of an international regulatory framework would remain open” (A/HRC/WG.10/1/CRP.2: 5). This cautious approach of states to regulating PMSCs was visible from the first session, as was their tendency to multiply the issues considered contentious – including the distinction between private military and private security (and the definitions thereof), the need to fully understand the nature of the business, the importance of consolidating national legislations, and the link to the UN Guiding Principles on BHR. It was clear from the beginning that consensus over the form of any international regulation was far from being reached: “Some delegations cautioned against discussing matters exclusively related to the draft convention proposed by the Working Group on the use of mercenaries and suggested to the intergovernmental working group to consider other ways of regulating the activities of PMSCs”⁵ (p. 6). One of the arguments against the creation of an international convention was that it would be binding for states, but without any real effects for the PMSCs themselves; another pointed out that some of the principles referred to in the draft, such as the responsibility to protect, did not gather consensus. Certain delegations called for expert consultation from outside the WGM and underlined the fact that the discussion on the WGM draft convention was “premature.”

Each intervention led to a questioning of the foundations laid by the WGM, the result being that, in practice, the work of the OEIGWG1 started from scratch and did not build on the progress achieved by the WGM. On the contrary, it was visible that the WGM’s proposal would not be endorsed by a majority of states. In its concluding remarks, the EU delegation suggested that the OEIGWG should not address the proposed draft convention but consider “other options” (A/HRC/WG.10/1/CRP.2: 15). The UK delegation expressed satisfaction with the existing framework of self-governance through the ICoC (most likely as a result of the existence of a relatively powerful British Association of Private Security Contractors), while Switzerland also saluted the existing regulatory framework. The US delegation was even clearer in opposing the idea of a convention, stating that the implementation of existing regulations was the main challenge. On the opposite end, Honduras, Algeria, Nigeria (on behalf of the African Group), South Africa, and Zimbabwe all supported the creation of a new international convention. Since the first session of the OEIWG1 in 2011, there was a clear cleavage between North and South on the issue of creating a legally binding instrument⁶. This cleavage also separated states where PMSCs are based (home states) and states where they recruit personnel or where they conduct operations and would become more and more visible in the sessions of the OEIGWG1 that followed.

⁵ The reports of the meetings are often inconsistent in their specifications of which particular delegations held a certain position. Sometimes, the states are mentioned by name, but other times the formulation is very ambiguous, only mentioning the arguments raised, and not the particular delegations making them.

⁶ The terms “North” and “South” are used here to distinguish between the developed countries, which most often are the countries of registration of PMSCs (home states), and which also have national legal frameworks, and the less developed ones, which most often are the countries where the PMSCs personnel is recruited but also the states where PMSCs operate (territorial states). Neither the “North”, nor the “South” acted as a block in the negotiation; however, there are visible similarities in the positions of both groups of countries which allow to make a clear distinction between a generally pro-regulation stance of the global South – with some exceptions – and a generally opposed stance of the global North.

The second session of the OEIGWG1 took place in August 2012 and the main subject under discussion was the opportunity to create a new regulation instrument. 65 states, two international organizations, the ICRC, and six NGOs participated – among them, only the ICJ had also taken part in the first session. The Working Group heard presentations from the perspective of the industry (held by Chris Sanderson, chair of the Security in Complex Environments Group – a British PSC), on the existing Montreux and ICoC regulatory frameworks (held by Dr. Nils Melzer, Swiss Chair of International Humanitarian Law, Geneva Academy and Research Director, Business & Human Rights, University of Zurich) and on the option to develop a new instrument (held by James Cockayne, an international lawyer who presents himself as “non-governmental participant in the Montreux process” and former “co-chair of the working group on governance established by the Transitional Steering Committee for the ICoC.”). The latter argued for upholding and enforcing the existing framework, while strongly criticizing the WGM draft convention. The WGM chair, Faiza Patel, intervened to uphold the need for an international convention in response to both the gaps in national regulation and in the international framework. There was also a lengthy submission by the International Commission of Jurists, which supported the creation of a new legally binding instrument and mentioned that certain activities such as detention or interrogation of prisoners should not be subcontracted.

At the second meeting, consensus seemed even more unlikely, since some of the participants questioned the competence of the Human Rights Committee to discuss issues related to international humanitarian law. In this context, the EU delegation suggested enlarging the circle of stakeholders by co-opting other fora, such as the International Maritime Organization, the Legal Committee of the GA, or the International Law Commission (A/HRC/22/21: 14). Several delegations underlined the “complexity” of the issues at hand, a way to suggest that the time was not ripe for actual negotiations on a draft text and that a “one-size-fits-all” solution was impossible. The North-South cleavage was once again visible, as several delegations also argued that more time should be given to the Montreux document and ICoC to prove their effectiveness, or that an international convention was useless if, in the absence of consensus, states would not ratify it (Canada, Belgium). On the other side, Egypt, Pakistan, Venezuela, and China reiterated their support for a Convention, while France and Algeria kept to a more neutral position.

The 2014 session of the OEIGWG1 was even more diluted in terms of issues addressed. Unlike the previous two sessions, it was not supported by supplementary documentation. Participation decreased to sixty states and would continue to decrease during the following sessions. The only NGO that participated consistently was the ICJ; all the others showed up only once. Among them, one initiative is especially notable: the Coalition for the Control of PMSCs, a NOVACT initiative, participated in 2014 but disappeared afterward. No new points were brought up; delegations were content to repeat their previous positions. Both consolidation of national legislations and the enforcement of existing self-regulatory frameworks and good practices, seemed to gain consensus as the easiest way forward. The discussion focused on the distinction between military and security companies – a distinction that would also appear in the text submitted at the end of the OEIGWG1’s works.

The fourth session, which took place the following year, was much more consistent in terms of active state engagement (although the number of participating states decreased even further), as several states and institutions submitted written statements in favor (Cuba, Brazil, South Africa, Pakistan, Iran, the African Group) or against (Norway, Mexico) the creation of an international convention. A position document submitted by the EU requested the enlargement of the consultation basis to the Montreux Document Forum and the ICoC Association, suggested the application of the UN Guiding Principles on Human Rights to PMSCs, and proposed the consideration of other possibilities

for regulation, such as international standard-setting, good practices, guidelines, or mutual assistance programs. It also deplored the lack of flexibility evinced by certain states, who insisted on discussing the draft proposed by the WGM (A/HRC/30/47). During this session, the WGM pushed for a discussion of the contentious issues by submitting a “concept note” in which it reiterated some of its fundamental positions, such as the existence of inherently state functions that cannot be outsourced, and the establishment of a grievance mechanism for ensuring remedies for human rights violations. This sparked fierce opposition from Western states, who once more rejected the WGM's draft convention and its attempt to structure the discussion around its principles. The United States submitted a written statement, asserting that “states do not need a new legally binding international instrument to develop effective national regulation of this industry” and emphasizing that the process ran parallel to the elaboration of the Business and Human Rights regulations, making it counterproductive. The rupture between the WGM and the OEIGWG1 was now very clear, as was the impossibility of reaching any kind of consensus.

These circumstances were made explicit during the fifth session of the OEIGWG1 (2016), when the chair-rapporteur, as well as the EU in its closing remarks, suggested that the Group end its activities. The sixth session of the group was therefore also the last, during which the OEIGWG1 presented its report. Only forty-two states participated, which shows the decreasing state interest in the subject. The report contains a four-page text entitled *Discussion document: elements for an international regulatory framework on the regulation, monitoring and oversight of the activities of PMSCs*. Its nature is unclear since no agreement was ever reached about the form of any international regulation. It is a working document: the “constructive ambiguity” has been underlined in the Report of the working group as one of its qualities (A/HRC/36/36: 7). It is important to note that point 3 of the discussion document repeats the same principles first stated by Chris Sanderson, the industry representative, in his presentation at the second session of the OEIGWG in 2012 – and with the same wording: effectiveness, inclusiveness, transparency and affordability (see also A/HRC/22/41: 9). Accountability, however, is missing from these principles, revealing once more the leverage exercised by the industry in the drafting process. In addition, the discussion document only contains loose provisions on the competencies of contracting states, territorial states, home states, and states of nationality of employers. The discussion on a binding instrument was clearly mired in a stalemate. This is when the HRC intervened.

On the basis of the OEIGWG1's report, the HRC established the *Open-Ended Intergovernmental Working Group to elaborate the content of an international regulatory framework, without pre-judging the nature thereof, to protect human rights and ensure accountability for violations and abuses related to PMSCs* (OEIGWG2) in 2017. The wording in its title – “without prejudging the nature thereof” – is the key to understanding the evolution of the discussion. Since no consensus was reached on the nature of the document to be produced, the chair-rapporteur of the OEIGWG1 decided to freeze the discussion on this issue and instead attempt to advance the conversation on the *content* of the regulation. The creation of the second working group was thus the direct result of the existing stalemate. It is worth noting that the last chair of the OEIGWG1 (elected in 2016) was subsequently elected to chair the newly-created group: Nozipho Joyce Mxakato-Diseko is from South Africa, a state widely known for its position in favor of a binding regulatory framework, and, as will be seen below, she has played a prominent role in pushing forward the discussions on a draft text.

The OEIGWG2's point of departure was the discussion document mentioned above. If the results achieved by the OEIGWG1 were meager in comparison to the large number of documents, reports and studies produced by the WGM, then it must be said that although the OEIGWG2 has only

met three times and produced only three reports since its establishment in 2017, it seems to be more efficient in terms of content delivery. A much larger number of states, NGOs and stakeholders submitted written statements, even if their positions have not changed significantly. The cleavages persist between those who consider the Montreux Document and the ICoC to be sufficient instruments of regulation and those who believe that they are too weak to ensure accountability. Instead, a different path forward emerges: the WGM's representative began to insist that regulation should focus not on the PMSCs *per se*, but on the *services* they offer, in order not to raise concerns about too much state intervention in the private sector. Indeed, "three delegations emphasized that the working group should resist the temptation to discuss in detail the internal regulations of PMSCs to avoid giving the impression that it intended to involve itself too deeply in the internal affairs of the businesses" (A/HRC/42/36:13). Thus, not only have PMSCs become legitimate businesses, but they have found a platform from which to accuse state actors of getting too involved in their regulation. In addition, several states began to claim that PMSCs should not be considered in any way as "armed groups" under customary international humanitarian law (that is, IHL should not apply to them), because they only provide a "business service" and are not a party to any given conflict (A/HRC/42/36: 12)⁷. This argument further reveals the metamorphosis of PMSCs from quasi-mercenaries into honorable transnational actors who can claim to be legitimate stakeholders in the regulation process.

During the second session of the OEIGWG2, which was postponed to 2021, the EU representative expressed doubts as to the utility of the discussion, given that other instruments such as the Montreux Document and the ICoC already existed. The United States reaffirmed their opposition to a binding instrument, while other states reiterated their support (South Africa, Cuba, India, Iran, Pakistan, Venezuela) (A/HRC/48/65). The cleavage was once again clear between two opposing positions: one that argued for the necessity of international regulation in the field (supported by the ICJ, the WGM, the WG on transnational corporations, and other business enterprises) and the other that believed national regulation should be strengthened and that the existing international framework was sufficient (A/HRC/48/65). Despite these opposing positions, Nozipho Joyce Mxakato-Diseko insisted on sticking to a discussion of the text that was initially presented and managed to develop its very schematic structure into a more elaborate text, holding discussions on the wording of different provisions.

Although delegations did not reach an agreement on the nature of the text, that is, *without prejudging the nature thereof*, the final version of the draft presented by the chair-rapporteur in October 2022 has all the elements of an international convention (a preamble, provisions on signature, ratification, accession and entry into force) – except for the title, which is: "Revised Zero Draft Instrument on an International Regulatory Framework on the Regulation, Monitoring of and Oversight Over the Activities of PMSCs." A comparison between this text and the "Draft of a Possible Convention" proposed by the WGM in 2011 reveals key differences that will be discussed below.

The first paragraph has eliminated the reference to "the *erga omnes* obligations related to the protection of human rights" and does not contain any reference to human rights. While most of the WGM's preamble refers to human rights and IHL, the preamble of the Revised Zero Draft dwells on the process of its creation, recalling the various HRC resolutions that led to the text, and only refers to human rights and IHL by recalling the 1949 Geneva Conventions. It also includes references to the Montreux Document, the ICoC and the UN Guiding Principles on business and human rights. In contrast to the WGM proposal, which expresses concern about the outsourcing of "inherently state functions,"

⁷ The Report does not mention which delegation held this position.

the new text acknowledges the “assistance” provided by PMSCs to states and international organizations. However, the “Definitions” section recycles the original WGM text by referring to “state functions” (the term *inherently* has disappeared). Mention is made that PMSCs are prohibited from exercising state functions such as direct participation in hostilities, combat operations, or interrogation of prisoners, but the document expects that national legislations should enforce this provision. In the most recent version, the section dedicated to the objectives of the instrument focuses on the protection of human rights and IHL, as well as on the accountability of PMSCs and remedies for victims of abuses, but the burden of enforcement falls to states and their national legislations. One of the most relevant provisions in the entire document is article 4(2), which states: “[Signatory states][states Parties] [undertake to][shall] take appropriate steps to criminalise in their domestic law abuses by PMSCs and their personnel of international human rights law and violations of International Humanitarian Law, specifically, but not limited to, war crimes, crimes against humanity, genocide, grave violations of the Geneva Conventions of 1949 and their Additional Protocols of 1977, and other crimes under international law.”

No further UNOEIGWG2 meetings have taken place since the publication of the Revised Zero Draft in October 2022. It was discussed in an informal meeting held in December 2022, but no public information on the discussion is available. The next formal meeting of the working group is to take place at the end of April 2023. Considering the positions that various states held during previous meetings, three possible outcomes are conceivable: a further dilution of the text through numerous amendments, a postponement of an agreement on the text by means of endless interventions, or a further decrease in participation by member-states. Most importantly, the discussion over the binding versus non-binding nature of the instrument has still not been addressed. However, recent developments in international politics, such as the massive presence of mercenaries in Ukraine, might also have an important effect on the inclination of states to further develop the regulation of this sector.

Conclusions

By analyzing the documents produced by these three groups, this article has elucidated the three simultaneous processes of dilution of the content of the norm forbidding mercenarism in the form of PMSCs: the first transferred the discussion from independent expert to state officials; the second was the negotiation process itself, as states with opposing views could only reach a consensus on issues involving the lowest common denominator; the third involved the multiplication of regulatory fora, as well as of types of stakeholders/actors involved.

The transfer of the discussion from experts to state representatives was accompanied by an effort by the latter to grasp the complexity of the issue, and the discussions in the OEIGWGs thus often showed the struggle of states to address the various aspects of the issue. During the intergovernmental negotiations, the factors that led to the dilution of the discussions were the absence of consensus over the form of the text to be adopted by the WG (binding/non-binding; on the base of the WGM draft or not); the multiplication of issues discussed (maritime issues, UN use of PMSCs, licensing issues, applicability of IHL, etc.); the insistence on relying on the existing framework versus adopting the WGM draft convention; the constant presence of industry representatives, but also the decreasing interest from states (there were 69 states participating at the first session of the OEIGWG, and only 42 states at the sixth). Several state representatives, especially from the North, proved very reluctant to engage in internationally binding law-making, insisting on the importance of national legislation. Thus, a North-South cleavage was also visible during the discussions. Northern states often have very solid domestic

PMSCs regulations, and considered them sufficient to address the issue, while Southern states suffer both from the lack of regulatory frameworks (or the capacity to enforce them) and from the heavy presence of foreign PMSCs on their territories. When PMSC employees commit human rights abuses on their territories, they might elude justice by both invoking extraterritoriality in the home state and foreign nationality in the territorial state.

The third process of dilution took place through the multiplication of participating actors and discussion fora. As the activities of the OEIGWGs revealed, there are a few NGOs and Swiss foundations that regularly took part in the debates: the ICRC (one of the initiators of the Montreux and ICoC processes), the ICoCA (which obviously represents the sector's interests), DCAF (the Geneva Center for Security Sector Governance, which is a Swiss government foundation) and the ICJ – which was the only NGO that is not actually linked either to states or business. Other NGOs have only appeared on occasion and without providing systematic input. This setting offered leverage to those organizations with greater resources and commitment to the process, making BINGOs ideally placed to influence the process.

The three dynamics outlined above led to a lost momentum for PMSC regulation. The opportunity structure, which appeared to favor regulation until around 2011, shifted the advantage to industry, which has gained more and more terrain in the last ten years, not only in practical terms, as it diversified its range of operations and territorial coverage, but also in symbolic terms, becoming almost an equal partner in the inter-governmental debates. The gradual intertwining of PMSC regulation and the BHR framework, highlighted in this research, does not account for the specific nature of the military and security, treating them as regular businesses, and marks the complete take-over by the market of these state functions.

However, while structural factors prove an ever greater obstacle to norm-emergence in the field, we cannot overlook the breakthroughs made by certain individual agents who made essential contributions to moving the agenda of regulation forward, such as Jose Gomez del Prado, Shaista Shameen, Faiza Patel and Nozipho Joyce Mxakato-Diseko. Thus, from a larger theoretical perspective, this article also points to the crucial role played by experts as agents in the process of norm-emergence. It is the experts who write ambitious draft proposals based on in-depth investigations of the issues on the ground. Nonetheless, they do not always possess the capacity to push their suggestions through the state-driven negotiation stage. At that point, as the research confirms, the absence of support from hegemonic powers, as well as of active transnational advocacy networks, hinders the emergence of regulatory norms covering the activity of PMSCs.

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